

DELAMINATION OF LAMINATED GLASS DURING BLAST LOADING EVENTS

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1 General Introduction

Designing for safety and resilience to large scale blast events has become a priority in the modern built environment. Whilst the whole structure needs to be designed accounting for these exceptional loads, it has been recognised that a large amount of the injuries and economic losses are caused by the damage to the façade structure, especially the glass elements [1]. Fragments of shattered windows can be propelled both inside and outside the building, causing significant injuries. Additionally, once the building skin is pierced, the blast pressure waves can enter through these openings causing additional wounds and damaging any equipment in the internal space.

Glass, as a brittle material, is not well suited to resist these sudden impulsive forces as no energy will be absorbed except through cracking and limited elastic displacements. Composite laminated glass windows can be used to minimize the damage and risk of injury during blast events. These are generally composed of layers of glass interposed by layers of polyvinyl butyral (PVB) membranes. These are bonded to the glass during the production process and hold the glass fragments in place once the glass layers are cracked by the blast forces. This ensures that glass fragments are kept in the window area and that blast pressures do not enter the internal space.

To achieve this all the laminated façade components need to be designed to resist the forces occurring during the blast event. Design parameters are therefore necessary both for the glass pane itself, for its supporting structure and for the connection between these two components. Full scale blast tests have been performed in the past employing 3D digital image correlation (DIC) to provide full field strain and displacement data for the whole glass surface. Additionally, strain gauges were placed on

the window support frame to measure the reaction forces generated during the test. These data were combined to produce overall reaction estimates for the whole perimeter, which showed that the forces on the supports seem to reach a plateau after the glass cracks. One of the possible mechanisms which could cause this behaviour is the progressive delamination of the glass fragments from the PVB membrane, as this could absorb significant amounts of energy.

In this research the behaviour of the laminated glass composite, and specifically the delamination mechanism, is examined in more detail employing laboratory experiments and models. To achieve this the PVB membrane was studied with tensile tests and it was attempted to fit a material model to the experimental data. The delamination of glass fragments was also considered in laboratory experiment and the resulting data were used to produce some finite element analysis (FEA) models of the process.

2 Method

2.1 PVB properties

Dr Hooper performed tensile tests of the PVB material. The interlayer material tested was Saflex PVB produced by Solutia Inc. with product number RB-41. The samples were cut in a dog bone shape for use in the tensile testing machine. The PVB overall length was 75mm. Its width was 4 mm, its gauge length was 20 mm and its thickness was 0.76 mm. The specimens were fixed to the machine fixings employing lightweight titanium alloy grips. The samples were tested at a range of speeds to produce different strain rate data. Speeds considered were 0.01 m/s, 0.1 m/s, 0.32 m/s, 1 m/s, 2 m/s, 5 m/s and 10 m/s therefore providing results for rates from

0.133 1/s to 133.33 1/s. All the tests were carried out in a servo-hydraulic Instron tensile testing machine. A lost motion device was used to guarantee a constant strain rate at the higher speed tests.

Data were recorded with a piezoelectric load cell for speeds above 0.1 m/s, and with a strain gauge load cell below this speed. The displacements were recorded from the testing machine's actuator arm.

The experimental results were then employed to produce a material model which could be used in finite element modelling. The aim was to produce a model which would be able to represent the nonlinear, rate dependent behaviour of the PVB material. Specifically, the high strain rate behaviour was considered as most important, as this would allow the material model to represent the membrane in glass delamination analyses.

It had been shown by Iwasaki [2] that the PVB behaviour is affected by the strain rate. At low strain rate it deforms as a rubbery hyperelastic material. However, when deformed at high strain rate it shows an initial stiff, almost linearly elastic phase. Following this, a plateau is reached followed by an exponential stiffening at high strains. Iwasaki does not attempt to include this high strain rate behaviour in his model. However, it was considered that this would need to be included in this case. Yang [3] in his paper develops a visco-hyperelastic model to represent the behaviour of polymeric material. To derive the hyperelastic part of the material model, the strain potential function is assumed to be of polynomial form, with 3 terms considered:

$$W = C10 * (I_1 - 3) + C01 * (I_2 - 3) + C11 * (I_1 - 3) * (I_2 - 3)$$

Where $i_1 = \lambda^2 + 2\lambda^{-1}$, $i_2 = \lambda^{-2} + 2\lambda$, λ is the stretch ($1 + \epsilon$) and C10, C01 and C11 are material constants. This potential can then be converted to a function relating the stress and strain quantities.

These principles are employed in the present work, however the three-term polynomial shown above is not considered sufficient to model the PVB behaviour. Specifically, the initial stiff behaviour could not be represented without including some additional terms. Therefore five polynomial terms were included here:

$$W = C10 * (I_1 - 3) + C01 * (I_2 - 3) + C11 * (I_1 - 3) * (I_2 - 3) + C20 * (I_1 - 3)^2 + C02 * (I_2 - 3)^2$$

The material was assumed to be incompressible, and this energy function was converted to a stress strain relation valid for uniaxial load cases following the method employed by Yang. The final result, after some manipulation is:

$$\sigma_e = \frac{1}{\lambda^4} * \left(2 * (\lambda^3 - 1) * (2 * C02 + 3 * C11 * \lambda + C01 * \lambda^2 - 6 * C02 * \lambda^2 + 4 * C02 * \lambda^3 + C10 * \lambda^3 - 3 * C11 * \lambda^2 - 3 * C11 * \lambda^3 + 3 * C11 * \lambda^4 + 4 * C20 * \lambda^2 - 6 * C20 * \lambda^3 + 2 * C20 * \lambda^5) \right)$$

The viscoelastic aspect of the behaviour was included using a Prony series approach. The instantaneous hyperelastic model is multiplied by an infinite series function of time.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0(\epsilon) * g(t)$$

With

$$g(t) = g_\infty + \sum_1^N g_i \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right)$$

In total 6 critical times were considered, ranging from 2.45×10^{-5} s to 10s. As dynamic mechanical analysis tests had been carried out, the time periods used for their analyses were considered. The constants for each critical time were fitted again with the tensile tests data.

To produce this fit, the mathematical method shown by Goh [4] was employed through an Excel spreadsheet.

Different fits were attempted. Firstly, the model was fitted to all the experimental data available for all the experimental rates. Secondly, a fit was produced for the high strain rate cases (above 1m/s), and finally for the low strain rates (below 1 m/s).

The resulting parameters were employed for the delamination models.

2.2 Delamination

The results of blast tests performed by Hooper [5] indicate that the reaction forces reach a plateau and do not significantly increase at high central deflections after the initial cracking of the glass. One of the possible energy absorption mechanisms assumed to cause this behaviour was the progressive delamination of the glass fragments from the PVB membrane.

Hooper performed some tensile tests on pre-cracked laminated glass to observe this behaviour.

The test samples were 150mm long and 60mm wide. Different PVB thicknesses were employed, however the results for the samples with 1.52mm thick PVB membranes are considered here. 3mm thick glass leaves were used for all the samples.

The samples were pre cracked. The glass was scored at 3 different regular spacing, 20mm, 10mm and a single score in the sample's center. They were then cracked following these scores. Additionally, randomly cracked samples were produced by repeatedly hitting the glass to produce a finely cracked pattern.

The samples were then tested using an Instron servo hydraulic testing machine, producing force displacement curves for the different conditions.

The tests were run at several speeds varying between 0.1 m/s and 10 m/s.

Data on the reaction force were collected employing a piezoelectric load cell, whilst the displacement could be measure directly through the machine. Photoelasticity data was also collected during some of the tests. This was achieved by positioning polarization filters between a light source and the sample and between the sample and the high speed camera. The two filters would be rotated 90° between each other, theoretically allowing only light whose polarization had been rotated by the stress condition in the material to be recorded by the camera.

The results from the tests were employed to calibrate FEA models of the cracked system.

The models created attempted to represent the test samples being employed in the experiments. The modelled sample was the same height as the experimental sample, 150mm, whilst the width was reduced to 30mm to increase the computational efficiency of the analysis. A symmetry condition

applied at the central edge. The PVB layer was modelled as 1.52mm thick, and the glass fragments were modelled as 20mm high and 3mm thick at this stage. The element size was 1mm³ in the glass, creating 3 elements through the glass thickness. The PVB elements size was 1mm x 1mm x 0.76mm, allowing the mesh of the membrane and of the glass to match exactly on the surface and the PVB thickness to be split in 2 elements. 3D stress elements with full integration were used for the PVB to avoid hourglassing issues. The glass elements could instead be modelled with reduced integration 3D stress elements to increase the speed of execution.

A key aspect of the model was the representation of the cohesive behaviour between the PVB and the glass fragments. The bond in laminated glass is achieved through hydrogen links between the polyvinyl butyral molecule and the silanol groups on the glass without the addition of specific adhesive compounds [6]. This bond is dependent on a number of factors connected with the surface treatments applied to both substrates and the temperatures and pressures adopted during the bonding process. Miller and Berg [7] studied the effect of different silane based surface treatments on the bond energy. Nguyen and Berg [8] also produced studies related to this topic. Their tests consisted on measuring the failure strength of the bond between PVB and glass beads and showed that treatments can significantly increase the bond strength.

Jagota [9] produced compressive shear tests to measure the bond capacity of PVB to glass in laminated glass sheets. He performed the test at different strain rates, producing stress strain plots for the various conditions. These tests were considered significant to the present problem, and were employed to produce the cohesive model of the laminated glass.

The cohesive zone was modelled employing the cohesive element formulation provided in ABAQUS 6.10. A layer of 3D cohesive elements 10⁻⁵ m thick was created on each side of the PVB membrane and contact conditions were set between each of these layers and the glass fragments. The material was modelled with a traction elastic law before the bond failure. As the software does not allow for nonlinear material properties to be applied to cohesive elements, a short term young modulus of PVB, 70 MPa, was used. The density used was of 1000

kg/m³. The failure mechanism was simulated using a quadratic maximum stress condition. The failure peak stresses were derived from Jagota's results. As the strain rates experienced in the model would be higher than those used in his tests, an empirical exponential law was fit to his data and extrapolated to the relevant rates (see Figure 1).

The limiting stresses listed in Table 1 were used.

The damage evolution mechanism available in ABAQUS was used. The degradation was considered to be linear, with no residual strength once the maximum displacement was reached. The values for the maximum displacements at this stage were fitted using the experimental data for each speed. Reaction force against displacement plots were produced for comparison with the experiments. The overall model can be seen in Figure 2.

3 Results

3.1 PVB properties

A selection of the experimental results of the PVB tensile tests can be seen in Figure 3. As was discussed previously, the material exhibits a transition in its behaviour between low rates and high rates similar to that observed between experiments conducted below and above the glass transition temperature. The 0.316 m/s line in the graph shows a typical low strain rate result. The curve shows gradual changes in gradient, with these changes being consistent with the hyperelastic behaviour of the material. The 10 m/s line shows different characteristics. At low strains the material now exhibits a much higher stiffness, showing an almost linear elastic behaviour until the plateau level (in this case roughly 12 MPa) is reached. This behaviour starts being evident from tests performed at 1 m/s.

The results outlined above were employed to produce a material model fit as explained in the previous section. Figure 3 shows the model results when fitted using all the available data at all speeds. As can be seen, the model does not represent accurately the lower strain rate cases. The two fits covering only the low rates or the high rate cases are shown respectively in Figure 4 and Figure 5. The low rate fit did not produce a model which could closely represent the material. However the high rate

fit seems to represent the higher speed results more closely.

It is therefore the case that no single set of parameters produced with the method outlined above seems to represent both the high rate and the low rate cases accurately. Table 2 shows the parameters which were fit for the high rate case.

The current model does not seem to be able to describe the fundamental shift in behaviour for the low strain conditions, whilst it seems to represent sufficiently either set of data. Therefore, the appropriate set of coefficients should be employed to model the phenomena of interest. The high rate parameters were used in the cohesive modelling below.

3.2 Cohesive results

Force displacement curves for each crack spacing and speed combination were produced from the tensile tests on the cracked specimens. A sample of these can be seen in Figure 8.

As can be seen, in all cases the curves' form is similar to what was observed during the analysis of blast tests data [10]. The samples show rapid stiffening at very low strains, followed by plateau levels of force being maintained until the samples fail at high strain levels.

The photoelasticity videos (Figure 6) show that progressive delamination occurs during a test. It can be seen that the delamination fronts move within the glass facets as the test progresses, until they eventually become detached from the central membrane. Energy will therefore be absorbed by this process.

The results were employed to calibrate the FEA models. Figure 7 shows that delamination takes place in the model, progressing each side of the glass crack width with time. The models displayed the same force displacement behaviour (see Figure 8 for sample results). The curves differ at low strains, overshooting the plateau level significantly before settling at roughly 0.05-0.1 strain. After this point the behaviour is close to the experimental results.

4 Conclusion

The constituent materials of the cracked laminated glass composite material have been considered in

this work. Experiments have been performed both on the PVB material and on the overall laminate. These have shown the highly non-linear behaviour of the overall system and of its individual components. The experimental data collected were employed to produce a visco-hyperelastic material model for the PVB membrane and to calibrate a delamination model to represent the whole system. Whilst improvements can be made for the initial small strain performance of the FEA model to represent more closely the measured behaviour, the latter parts of the curves are similar to the experimental data.

Further work will be devoted to improving the PVB material model fit. Different material models will be tested to attempt to include the low strain rate behaviour and to increase the correlation across the rates' range.

More FEA models will also be produced to assess the impact of more irregular crack patterns, especially considering cracks in different positions on the two sides of the PVB membrane and vertical cracks connecting the parallel horizontal cracks. Additional experiments might also be performed to add specific data sets for these cracking conditions and to increase the number of available speeds for comparison with modelling. This would facilitate an investigation of useful links between these factors and the cohesive parameters used in the model.

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Table 1: Peak stresses employed in modeling

Test speed (m/s)	Peak cohesive stress (MPa)
1	9.48
3.16	10.38
10	11.28

Table 2: Material model fitted to high rate experimental data

Parameter	Value
C01	829.4
C10	-686.7
C11	-535.9
C20	146.0
C02	756.8
τ_1	0.673
τ_2	0.114
τ_3	0
τ_4	0.0584
τ_5	0
τ_6	0.0553

Figure 1: Logarithmic plot of peak stress from Jacota's shear experiments

Figure 2: Isometric and side view of the FEA model used to model the delamination phenomenon

Figure 3: Experimental results with a material model fit. The model coefficients were produced including all the experimental rates

Figure 4: Experimental results with a material model fit. The model coefficients were produced including the low rate data sets (from 0.01 to 0.316 m/s).

Figure 5: Experimental results with a material model fit. The model coefficients were produced including the high rate data sets (from 1 to 10 m/s).

Figure 6: Three images from the photoelasticity data for one experiment. The three images show the progress of the delamination fronts through the glass fragments.

Figure 7: Images from the ABAQUS delamination model. The delamination fronts can be followed noting the area of glass with significant stress levels. These reduce as the simulated time progresses.

Figure 8: Experimental stress strain data and FEA model results for the cracked laminated glass tensile tests. The FEA results display an initial peak not evident in the experiment's results. The plateau levels are similar.